

Station: H₂O Usage

△ 1000 liter H₂O per year

Select your scenario!

from **A** (H₂O -low)
to **D** (H₂O -high)

Guiding questions:

The guiding questions will help you to gradually understand the differences between the scenarios and maintain an overview.

- I spend ... per day on social media.**
- I prefer to visit ... social media sites [A].**
- I post ... on social media**
- In everyday life, I use ...**
- I watch ... videos per day in real time (Streaming) [B].**
- I watch ... videos per day in real time (streaming) [B].**
- I play ... video games on my smartphone every day.**

No blocks

A

B

C

D

< 10 min

< 1 h

< 3 h

≥ 3h

none

WhatsApp /
YouTube /
Twitch /
X (Twitter)

Facebook /
Snapchat /
Instagram

Pinterest /
Reddit /
TikTok

... just a few
highlights per
year

... every month

... every week

... (almost) daily

... Wi-Fi.

... Wi-Fi, except
for small
tasks(emails, ...).

... sometimes
Wi-Fi,
sometimes
mobile data.

... mostly
mobile data

... none

< 1 h

1-3 h

> 3 h

SD (480p)
or less

HD (720p)

Full-HD
(1080p)

4k

< 4 h

≥ 4 h

\

\

[A] If none or more the one of the above options apply, please select option C (3 blocks).

[B] Streaming involves playing audio and video content in real time, meaning that it does not need to be downloaded previously (Cloudflare. (n.d.). Was ist Streaming? | Wie Streaming von Videos funktioniert. Retrieved March 30, 2025, from <https://www.cloudflare.com/de-de/learning/video/what-is-streaming/>).